

AN ASSESSMENT ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS AT CAPUAL NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL, MINISTRY OF BASIC, HIGHER AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION-SULU

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ABSTRACT

The study is a descriptive research which deals with the assessment on the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE - Sulu. It also deals with the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of gender, age, grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income, the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu in terms of school facilities, peer relationship, and parental involvement. It also deals with the significant difference in the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to demographic profile in terms of gender, age, grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income, and the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu. The study was conducted at Capual National High School particularly at Bulaghaw, Capual Island, Omar, Sulu. The respondents of the study are the high school students of Capual National High School. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents of the study. The research instrument is composed of two parts. Part I is about the demographic profile of the respondents which includes their gender, age, grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income. Part II is composed of 10 statements each on school facilities, peer relationship, and parental involvement. There are 5 levels to choose from which ranges from “always” to “never”. It was found that majority of the junior high school students of Capual National High School are females, in their right age for their present grade level, almost equal number were taken from each gender, the parents are not very educated, and belong to low income family. School facilities and parental involvement often affect the academic performance of the students while peer relationship sometimes affect it. There is no significant difference in terms of demographic profile. There is a moderate

correlation among the school facilities and peer relationship and a low correlation in terms of parental involvement.

Keywords: *Academic performance, School Facilities, Peer Relationship, Parental Involvement.*

INTRODUCTION

Academic performance is the building block of quality education. It has a great contribution to worldwide growth of social and economic development. It is an indicator of the quality of education. The result of the performance rating of the school in National Achievement Test, College Entrance Examination, and future education of the students reflects its form of academic development ranging from kindergarten to junior high school. Such that, frequent poor performance rating of the school and low achievements of the students can be taken as indicative of possibly lack of sense of commitment and efficacies among the faculty of the school, collective efforts, participative school management, and sound decision making.

According to philosophy, education is a weapon whose effect depends on who holds it his arms and at whom it is aimed. One of the factors that are helpful in academic development is a participative learning process which is grounded from the ability of teachers to employ effective strategies that inspire and allow practically all learners to engage themselves actively and willingly share ideas with peers in the interactive learning activities. Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978) attributes the development of the brain's higher order processes to parents, caregivers, peers, and society at large. According to this theory, cultural variations could exist as social interaction is necessary for human growth. The method places a strong emphasis on how social contact influences personal development. It suggests that social interactions with more experienced individuals around us mold our cognitive capacities and that learning is mostly a social process in humans. It emphasizes how people who act as mentors in our lives—like parents and teachers—have an impact on how we develop psychologically.

Ampofo et.al (2015), Department of Interdisciplinary Studies, College of Agriculture Education, University of Education Winneba, Ghana-West Africa, Mampong-Ashanti. Media measures how much a student's academic aspirations and efforts affect their academic success in Ghana's public senior high schools. The academic performance of senior high school students in Ghana's Ashanti Mampong Municipality was investigated in this study along with a number of significant features. Data for both correlational and descriptive research types were gathered using questionnaires. A multi-stage sampling strategy produced a sample size of 571 students as a result. The study's findings showed the connections between a child's academic achievement and their own, their parents', and their own education. The findings also demonstrated that the child's effort, the mother's level of education, the child's sex, and the child's desire for education were the main determinants of academic accomplishment. Again, the outcomes refuted

the null hypothesis. These findings led to the recommendation that parents ensure that their kids spend a lot of time reading and that they are ready to support them through challenging periods. Students should be encouraged to have high academic goals by education stakeholders.

Younas, et al. (2020) PhD in Education at Soochow University, Suzhou, China's School of Education. Effects of the Home Environment on Academic Performance in Higher Education Students. This study aims to explore the relationship between a student's home environment and academic success. The study's main objective is to look at the connection between the family environment and academic achievement of Pakistani students. A self-administered questionnaire from four Pakistani provinces was utilized to gather data from 300 respondents as part of a descriptive survey research design. A stratified random sampling method was used to select a sample of the respondents. To evaluate the data, regression analysis was employed. The result is explained using three different forms of analysis: demographic data, inferential analysis, and descriptive analysis. The results of the study indicated a slender positive correlation between students' familial environment and academic success. It is also revealed that perceptions about gender-specific academic achievement and the family environment are the same for males and girls in the same status. Finally, recommendations were sent to legislators, parents, and school administrators.

Research Questions

It aimed to find answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gender;
 - 1.2 Age;
 - 1.3 Grade level;
 - 1.4 Parent's educational attainment; and
 - 1.5 Parent's average monthly income?
2. What is the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE-Sulu in terms of:
 - 2.1 School facilities;
 - 2.2 Peer relationship; and
 - 2.3 Parental involvement?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE-Sulu when data are grouped according to demographic profile in terms of the following:
 - 3.1 Gender;
 - 3.2 Age;
 - 3.3 Grade level; and
 - 3.4 Parent's educational attainment?
4. Is there a significant correlation between the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE-Sulu in terms of

- 4.1 School facilities;
- 4.2 Peer relationship; and
- 4.3 Parental involvement?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this component, the researcher adopted the quantitative research method particularly the descriptive-explanatory research design.

Descriptive-explanatory research design is a suitable design in the collection, analysis, classification, tabulation, and interpretation of the desired information. It is an ideal research design in gauging quantitative data to formulate logical and reliable interpretation specifically regarding the extent of the factors affecting the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu in terms of school facilities, peer relationship, and parental involvement leading to address the needs for academic development.

Cristobal (2017) states that the purpose of descriptive research design is to collect data on certain features within a given topic of study. Its goal is to paint a picture of events as they occur. This kind of research doesn't entail any variable modification.

Research Locale

The researcher conducted the study at Capual National High School, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) – Sulu this current school year 2023-2024. Capual National High School, with a total student's population of 696 based on the official record (SF form) at the office of the OIC - principal, is located at Bulaghaw Capual Island, Omar, Sulu.

Bulaghaw Capual Island, Omar is among the municipalities under the 2nd district of Sulu, Philippines where the major sources of income of families are farming and fishing.

The researcher has been working as a secondary school teacher at Capual National High School since 2010 and has been cognizant of its existing issues and concerns. Thus, the researcher chooses the school as the research local of the study.

Respondents of The Study

The respondents of this study were the one hundred (100) randomly selected students among the 696 junior high school students of Capual National High School, MBHTE - Sulu.

The table below showed the distributions of samples in the research study.

Table 2

Grade level	Number of respondents	Total
Grade 7	25	25
Grade 8	25	25
Grade 9	25	25
Grade 10	25	25
Total	100	100

Sampling Design

The non-probability sampling design through purposive sampling method was employed in this study due to resources and time constraints. The use of purposive sampling technique was to ensure the representation of gender, age, grade level, civil status, and educational attainment variables among junior high school students.

Research Instrument

The research instrument of this study was adopted from the standardized research instrument of the study of Rosalind Martin, et.al (2015), entitled "Perceptions of Quality School Facilities" with minor alteration to make it suitable to the settings of the study grounded from its statement of the problem. Thus, the instrument of this study is a well-structured, adopted, and modified standardized questionnaire.

The survey questionnaire of this study covered the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu which was presented in two components. The first component was mainly about the demographic profile of the respondents such as gender, age, grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income. The second component was all about the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu in terms of its sub-categories such as school facilities, peer relationship, and parental involvement.

The questionnaire consisted of 30-item statements which were presented in three sub-categories. Each category Was made up of 10-item statements.

To gauge the extent of the academic performance of the junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu, the five-point Likert's Scale, as follows, was used: 5– always, 4- often, 3-sometimes, 2- for rarely, and 1- never.

Data Gathering Procedure

In this study, the researcher applied the standard accepted protocol of the school of graduate studies of Sulu State College in securing authorization from specified offices to administer the survey questionnaire at the chosen research locale.

Insofar as the research design of the study is descriptive- explanatory, the researcher used the five - point Likert scale to gauge the extent of the variables stipulated in the statement of the problem.

To administer the survey questionnaire of the study at the research locale in a permissible manner, the researcher acted upon the steps as follows:

- I. Requested a permit from the dean of the school of graduate studies of Sulu State College.
- II. Requested a permit from the office of the school's division superintendent, MBHTE – Sulu,
- III. Requested a permit from the office of the school principal/OIC of Capual National High School.

Prior to the conduct of the survey, the researcher gave a brief orientation regarding instructions on seat arrangement, on how to put a check mark on the appropriate box, as well as the manner of distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In order to make an accurate treatment of empirical data, leading to formulation of relevant analysis, interpretation, and evaluation, the researcher used the following statistical tools.

I. Frequency and Percentage.

Frequency and percentage was used to determine the demographic profile of the respondents such as gender, age, grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income.

II. Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation.

Weighted mean and standard deviation was used to determine the extent of the factors affecting the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE –Sulu in terms of school facilities, peer relationship, and parental involvement.

III. **t-test and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).** t-test for independent variable was used to determine the significant differences in the extent of the factors affecting the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE –Sulu when data were grouped according to respondent’s demographic profile such as gender. One-way analysis of variance was used to determine the significant differences in the extent of the factors affecting the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE –Sulu when data were grouped according to age, grade, level, parents ‘educational attainment, and parent’s average monthly income.

IV. Pearson Product – Moment Correlation.

Pearson product-moment correlation was used to determine the significant correlation between the extent of the factors affecting the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE –Sulu in terms of school facilities, peer relationship, and parental involvement.

V. To determine the extent of the factors affecting the academic performance of junior high school students at Capual National High School, MBHTE –Sulu, the researcher used the five - point Likert Scale table below:

LIKERT’S SCALE TABLE

Point	Scale value	Interpretation
5	4.5 – 5.00	Always
4	3.5 – 4.49	Often
3	2.5 – 3.49	Sometimes
2	1.5 – 2.49	Rarely
1	1.0 – 1.49	Never

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- 1. What is the demographic profile of the junior high school students of Capual National High School, MBHTE- Sulu in terms of 1.1 gender, 1.2 age, 1.3 grade level, 1.4 parent's educational attainment, and 1.5 parent's average monthly income?**

1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender. It showed that 75 or 73.5% of the respondents are females and only 27 or 26.5% are males.

The result implies that the female respondents outnumber the male respondent's in terms of gender.

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	27	26.5%
Female	75	73.5%
TOTAL	102	100%

1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 1.2 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age. Fifty-seven or 55.9% of the respondents each are between 14 – 16 years old and only 1 or 1% is 20 years old and above.

The result implies that more than half of the respondents are in their middle teens and only 1 is matured.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
13 years old and below	29	28.4%
14 – 16 years old	57	55.9%
17 – 19 years old	15	14.7%
20 years old and above	1	1.0%

TOTAL	102	100%
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1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Grade Level

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of grade level. It showed that almost equal number of respondents were taken from each grade level.

The result implies that the researcher tried her best to have equal representation from each grade level.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 7	24	23.5%
Grade 8	26	25.5%
Grade 9	27	26.5%
Grade 10	25	24.5%
TOTAL	102	100%

1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parent's Educational Attainment

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of parent's educational attainment. It showed that 62 or 60.8% of the parents reached elementary level in education while 1 or 1% finished a doctorate degree.

The result implies that majority of the parents were less educated and only less than 20% are very educated.

Table 1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
No Formal Education	7	6.9%
Elementary Level	62	60.8%
Secondary Level	16	15.7%
College Level	14	13.7%

Master's Degree	2	2.0%
Doctorate Degree	1	1.0%
TOTAL	102	100%

1.5 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parent's Average Monthly Income

Table 1.5 presents the demographic profile of the respondents' in terms of parent's average monthly income. It showed that 81 or 79.4% of the parents earn P5,000.00 and below each month and only 3 or 2.9% earn P15,001.00 and above each month.

The result implies that more than half of the respondents belong to low income family.

Table 1.5 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parent's Average Monthly Income

Parent's Average Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
P5,000.00 and below	81	79.4%
P5,001.00 – 10,000.00	12	11.8%
P10,001.00 – 15,000.00	6	5.9%
P15,001.00 and above	3	2.9%
TOTAL	102	100%

2. What is the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu in terms of 2.1 school facilities, 2.2 peer relationship, and 2.3 parental involvement?

Table 2.1 presents the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School in terms of school facilities.

It showed that the respondents indicated from **always** to **sometimes** on the different statements on school facilities. Among those they indicated **always** are; our school environment is clean and well – maintained which encourages us to focus on our studies (mean = 4.941, SD = .236); and our classroom is ventilated and clean, so it is comfortable for teaching and learning activities (mean = 4.500, SD = .728). For **sometimes**, some of the statements are; the class size of students is ideal for academic

development (mean = 3.412, SD = 1.402); and the teacher – student ratio does not follow the DepEd National recommendation which is disrupting the learning process and hampering our hope to improve academic performance (mean = 3.039, SD = 1.954). The average mean of 3.965 means that school facilities **often** affect the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School.

The result simply implies that school facilities can greatly affect the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School.

Table 2.1 Extent of the Academic Performance in terms of School Facilities

School Facilities	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Our school environment is clean and well – maintained which encourages us to focus on our studies.	4.941	.236	Always
There is adequate space for our teachers to work productively and inspires us to improve our academic performance.	4.049	1.631	Often
Our classroom is ventilated and clean, so it is comfortable for teaching and learning activities.	4.500	.728	Always
There is a sufficient speed and reliability of internet connection in our school which support instructional and learning practices.	4.333	1.137	Often
Our library is equipped with adequate references that boost our interest to read and improve our academic performance.	3.618	1.567	Often
6. Our school laboratory is equipped with adequate modern laboratory instruments that boost our interest to focus on academic improvement.	4.010	1.085	Often
7. The classrooms are enough that respond to students' need to engage in learning activities.	4.108	1.142	Often
8. The class size of students is ideal for academic development.	3.412	1.402	Sometimes
9. Our classroom is equipped with adequate armchairs which makes us comfortable to attend to the learning process and improve our academic performance.	3.637	1.646	Often
10. The teacher – student ratio does not follow the DepEd National recommendation which is disrupting the learning process and hampering our hope to improve academic performance.	3.039	1.954	Sometimes
AVERAGE	3.965		OFTEN

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always
4	3.50 – 4.49	Often
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes
2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely
1	1.00 – 1.49	Never

Table 2.2 presents the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School in terms of peer relationship.

It showed that the respondents indicated from **often** to **rarely** on the different statements and among those they indicated **often** are; to work with peers in classroom activities encourage me to be more active and improve my academic performance (mean = 4.412, SD = 0.916; and when I work with peers in class activities, I become more active and it brings up my academic performance (mean = 4.392, SD = 1.195). For **rarely**, some of the statements are; my peers persuade me to attend online games which distracts my academic performance (mean = 2.226, SD = 1.641); and my peers convince me to skip classes which distract my academic performance (mean = 2.128, SD = 1.663). However, they indicated **never** in only statement 7 and that is on; my peers persuade me to try cigarette smoking, it lessens my interest to focus on improving my academic performance (mean = 1.4714, SD = 0.951). The average mean of 3.199 means that peer relationship sometimes affects the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School.

The result implies that peer relationship can sometimes help improve the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School

Table 2.2 Extent of the Academic in terms of Peer Relationship

Peer Relationship	Mean	SD	Interpretation
My peers keep making bad joke about me and it distracts my academic development.	1.990	1.294	Rarely
When I work with peers in class activities, I become more active and it brings up my academic performance.	4.392	1.195	Often
My peers convince me to skip classes which distract my academic performance.	2.128	1.663	Rarely
Having studious peers encourages me to improve my study habits and develop my academic performance.	4.206	1.261	Often
Working with intelligent peers helps me learn the value of empathy, cooperation, and improve my solving problem skill.	3.784	1.122	Often

My peers are sluggish in school works; I can't focus on improving my academic performance.	3.716	1.498	Often
My peers persuade me to try cigarette smoking, it lessens my interest to focus on improving my academic performance.	1.471	.951	Never
My peers persuade me to attend online games which distracts my academic performance.	2.226	1.641	Rarely
9. I find improvement in working with peers during class discussions because I also learned the values of academic performance from them.	3.578	1.465	Often
10. To work with peers in classroom activities encourages me to to be more active and improve my academic performance.	4.412	.916	Often
AVERAGE	3.199		SOMETIMES

Table 2.3 presents the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School in terms of parental involvement.

The respondents indicated from *often* to *sometimes* on the different statements. Some of those statements they indicated *often* are; my parents check my study habit regularly to ensure improvement in my academic performance (mean = 4.402, SD =1.065); and my parents communicate with my teachers to monitor my academic performance (mean = 4.324, SD = 1.415). For *sometimes*, some of the statements are; my parents encourage me to go to libraries to further focus on academic performance (mean = 3.431, SD =1.732); and my parents portray a positive attitude about schools and education which enlighten me about the importance of academic performance (mean = 3.382, SD = 1.251). The average mean of 4.016 means that parental involvement *often* affects the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School.

The result simply implies that parental involvement often positively affects the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School.

Table 2.3 Extent of the Academic Performance in terms of Parental Involvement

Parental Involvement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My parents communicate with my teachers to monitor my academic performance.	4.324	1.415	Often
2. My parents check my study habit regularly to ensure improvement in my academic performance.	4.402	1.065	Often
3. My parents attend parents – teacher – community meeting and it encourages me to participate actively in our class discussion.	4.549	.740	Always
4. My parents attend our school activities and it inspires me to perform well in school.	4.245	.861	Often
5. My parents help me in a positive way in my homework which boost my interest in my academic improvements..	3.980	1.177	Often
6. My parents portray a positive attitude about schools and education which enlighten me about the importance of academic performance.	3.382	1.251	Sometimes
7. My parents encourage me to go to libraries to further focus on academic performance.	3.431	1.732	Sometimes
8. My parents check my class schedules to maintain my attendance and punctuality which make me attentive to academic performance.	3.333	1.471	Sometimes
9. My parents allow me to skip homework to participate in extra - curricular activities which lessen my interest in good academic performance.	4.118	1.458	Often
10. My parents reward me for good grades which inspires me to keep my good study habits and improve my academic performance.	4.400	1.435	Often
AVERAGE	4.016		OFTEN

3. *Is there a significant difference in the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to gender, age, grade level, parent’s educational attainment, and parents average monthly income?*

The t - test was used for gender since there are only two categories. The sig. value of 0.140 for school facilities are greater than the p= value of .05, the sig. value of 0.257 for

peer relationship is greater the p – value of .05, and the sig. value of 0.343 was also greater than the p = value of .05. It means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

There is no significant difference in the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School, MBHTE- Sulu when data are grouped according to their gender.

The result implies that gender is not a determinant on the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School. Their academic performance could be affected by other factors and has nothing to do with gender.

Younas, et al. (2020) found that the respondents indicated that there is no significant differences in the perception about academic performance and gender.

Table 3.1 t – test for Significant Difference in the Extent of the Academic Performance of Junior High School Students of Capual National High School when Data are Grouped in terms of Gender

Variables	Grouping	Mean		Diff.	t	Sig.	Description
		Mean	SD				
School Facilities	Male	3.050	.630				Not
	Female	3.230	.750	.180	18.490	.140	Significant
Peer Relationship	Male	3.550	.550				Not
	Female	3.740	.720	.190	24.150	.257	Significant
Parental Involvement	Male	3.210	.810				Not
	Female	3.980	.790	.770	20.650	.343	Significant

Significant at .05 level

In Table 3.2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used for age, grade level, parent’s educational attainment, and parent’s average monthly income. The sig. value of 0.542 for age is greater than the p - value of .05, the sig. value of 0.582 for grade level is greater than the p value at .05, the sig. value of 0.340 for parent’s educational attainment is greater than he p -value of .05, and the sig. value of 0.425 for parent’ average monthly income is also greater than the p - value of .05. It could only mean that the null hypothesis is accepted in terms of age, grade level, parent’s educational attainment, and parent’s average monthly income.

There is no significant difference in the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School when data are grouped

according to their age, grade level, parent’s educational attainment, and parent’s average monthly income.

The result suggests that the various demographic profiles are unable to forecast the level of academic achievement among Capual National High School junior high school pupils.

According to Ampofo (2015), the primary factors of academic performance are the child's efforts, gender, mother's education, and the child's desire for academic success.

Table 3.2 ANOVA for Significant Difference in the Extent of the Academic Performance of Junior High School Students of Capual National High School when Data are Grouped in terms of Age, Grade Level, Parent’s Educational Attainment, and Parent’s Average Monthly Income

		Sum of		Mean			
		Square	df	Square	f	Sig.	Description
AGE							
Groups	Between	.122	3	0.041	0.732	.542	Not
	Within Groups	5.525	98	0.056			Significant
	Total	5.647	101				
Grade Level							
Groups	Between	5.283	3	1.761	0.655	.582	Not
	Within Groups	263.472	98	2.688			Significant
	Total	268.755	101				
Parent’s Educational Attainment							
Groups	Between	8.301	5	1.660	0.665	0.340	Not
	Within Groups	239.788	96	2.498			Significant
	Total	248.088	101				

Total

Parent's Monthly Income	Average						
	5.555	3	1.852	0.940	.425		Not
Between Groups	193.151	98	1.971				Significant
Within Groups	198.706	101					
Total							

Significant at .05 level

4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu?

Pearson Product – Moment Correlation or Pearson r was used to determine if there is a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of school facilities, peer relationship, and parental involvement.

The average value of $r = 0.396$ for school facilities was interpreted as **moderate correlation** while the average value of $r = 0.403$ for peer relationship was interpreted as **moderate correlation** at significant value of .05 two- tailed test, and the average value of .254 for parental involvement was also interpreted as **low correlation**.

The result simply implies that the different factors has a **moderate correlation** as far as the extent of academic performance of junior high school students of Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu in terms of school facilities and peer relationship. However, parental involvement has little to do with the two factors.

Younas (2020) found a weakly positive link between a student's academic achievement and their family environment.

Table 4. Significant Correlation in the Extent of the Academic Performance of Junior High School Students of Capual National High School, MBHTE – Sulu

		Pearson r	Sig.	n	Description
	Peer				
School	Relationship	0.383	.000	102	Moderate
Facilities	Parental				
	Involvement	0.408	.000	102	Moderate
	AVERAGE	0.396			MODERATE
	School				
Peer	Facilities	0.592	.000	102	High
Relationship	Parental				
	Involvement	0.213	.000	102	Low
	AVERAGE	0.403			MODERATE
	School				
Parental	Facilities	0.203	.000	102	Low
Involvement	Peer				
	Relationship	0.304	.000	102	Low
	AVERAGE	0.254			LOW

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at $\alpha = .05$

Correlation Scales adapted from Hopkins (2002):

0.0– 0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1 – 0.3 = Low; 0.3 – 0.5 = Moderate; 0.5 – 0.7 = High;
0.7 – 0.9 = Very High; 0.9 – 1.0 = Nearly Perfect

Conclusions

The following was concluded based on the findings of the study:

The female students outnumber the male students in the junior high school of Capual National High School. Majority are in the middle teens in age. Most parents did not finish even high school, and earns below the minimum every month.

It only showed that school facilities and parental involvement can spell the difference between success and failure of the academic performance of the students. Peer relationship can also affect their academic performance sometimes.

The absence of difference in the extent of the academic performance among junior high school students of Capual National High School when data are grouped according to gender, age, grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income only proves that profiles of the students cannot exactly predict how good or how bad the academic performance of the students.

The moderate correlation in the extent of the academic performance among junior high school students of Capual National High School in terms of school facilities and peer relationship could only mean that the two factors are interrelated to some extent. However, parental involvement has an effect to the academic performance to some extent.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1. Further study on the extent of the academic performance among students may be conducted to ascertain the effect of the different factors on them.
2. Future researchers on the same topic may add variables like study habits, time management, and other variables not covered by this study.
3. Teachers may adapt effective approaches, methods, techniques for the enhancement on the academic performance of the students.
4. Schools may provide the learners an environment that is conducive to learning in order to improve their academic performance.
5. Parents may provide a home that is conducive to learning and must always get involve in their children's education.

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

First, a thorough informed consent form explaining the trial's goals, methods, potential risks and benefits, and confidentiality regulations was sent to each participant. Furthermore, since the personal information of the responders had no effect on the trial's results, all trial data points were painstakingly anonymized. To preserve participant privacy, data collection was done in a private environment, and the gathered information was kept in a safe archive that the researchers alone could access. Notwithstanding the disparities in viewpoints and opinions, each participant was accorded respect.

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